

Guidelines – Testing course material phase I

1. Description

In the framework of the In Silico World project, online lecture material (on the platform Toledo) on in silico medicine and in silico trials were developed for different stakeholder groups.

2. Participant group

Four mini-courses have been developed, each for a different participant group. The four participant groups are “Tech – Education”, “Tech – Retraining”, “NonTech – Education” and “NonTech – Retraining”. “Tech” refers to participants with a strong mathematical/technical background (e.g. in biomedical engineering). “NonTech” refers to participants in the domain of medicine/pharmaceutical/life sciences and allied health professions, who don’t have a strong mathematical or technical/computational background. “Education” refers to students at the master or PhD level, whereas “Retraining” refers to experts who are already working in the field (e.g. in the clinic or in industry).

3. General information

Each mini-course contains three modules, consisting of one or two parts. Each part includes a recording, together with the corresponding slides and a transcript. An overview of the different modules per participant group can be found in appendix A.

4. Access to the lecture material

1. To access the lecture material on Toledo, you can send a request to peter.stassen@kuleuven.be including the following information
 - your first and last name
 - your e-mail address
 - the envisioned use of the lecture material

Note that the lecture material can be used for academic and educational purposes only!

2. Activate your Toledo account
3. Go to Toledo: www.toledo.kuleuven.be
4. Open the “In Silico World” course

5. Join a group to participate and close the pop-up window

6. Test your prior knowledge
7. Click on "Course material"
8. Click on "Overview: NAME OF GROUP" (in this example: NonTech – Education)

9. Click on the upper right arrow, to go through the lecture material

Appendix A – Overview of the content of the mini-courses

Tech – Education

Module 1

Part A. What is a model?

A model is a commonly used term, but a description of what a model is, is much harder to find. This module tries to answer the general question “What is a model?”, which is relevant for many disciplines, including in silico medicine. The search for an answer leads to a convoluted journey along different perspectives, descriptions and types of models.

Part B. Introduction to in silico medicine

This course module introduces the participants to some of the general concepts of in silico medicine technologies and discusses the related opportunities and limitations.

Module 2

Part A: Regulatory aspects

With the perspective to integrate in silico medicine in the process of diagnosis, treatment development and treatment selection, a regulatory framework is unavoidable. This course module provides an overview of the state-of-the-art regarding the regulatory framework and the aspects that are still lacking.

Part B: VVUQ hands-on

In the framework of in silico modelling is not only the technical development of the models essential, but also its evaluation. This evaluation comprises a combination of verification, validation and uncertainty quantification of the model. In this course module, these concepts are introduced and the participants will practice them based on concept questions and apply them in an example model of an aortic aneurysm.

Module 3: Agent-based models

While many in silico medicine models represent the aggregated behaviour of a tissue or body part, an agent-based models utilizes an alternative approach, where individual agents and their mutual interaction play a central role. The course module explains the general model principles, their benefits, and illustrates the modelling technique with potential applications.

Tech – Retraining

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Module 2

Part A: Reliable measurement input

As in silico medicine models often require experimental or clinical measurements as input, the outcome of these models depends on these measurements. The importance of awareness of the reliability of the measurement input and its effect on the outcome is illustrated based on the C4Bio project.

Part B: VVUQ hands-on

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NonTech – Education

Module 1: Introduction to in silico medicine

This course module introduces the participants to some of the general concepts of in silico medicine technologies and discusses the related opportunities and limitations.

Module 2: Experimental validation of models

An in silico model can only be considered credible when it is properly validated with an experiment. The course module indicates how such a validation experiment can be developed and illustrates this with state-of-the-art examples.

Module 3: Example cases

This course module provides the participants with state-of-the-art examples of in silico medicine models that are in different stages of their development and have the perspective of being used in the clinical practice and/or the development of improved treatment strategies.

NonTech – Retraining

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